

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The article discusses the theoretical foundations of using teaching methods in the educational process to increase the effectiveness of teaching English as a foreign language. The project method and the method of motivation also allow to optimally solve many problems related to learning a foreign language by playing during the lesson. Here, the authors try to reveal the relevance of the above methods, especially their effectiveness in teaching English as a foreign language, and focus on the practical side of using this methodology.

Key words: project method, presentations, motivation, students' independent work.

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Learning a foreign language opens up an amazing future for everyone. Indeed, the largest language in the world is English. In this age of technology, most of the Internet is in English. The basis of the world globalization process is also the English language. In addition, we all know that English should be used at work, in financial institutions, tourism, transport, airlines, education and other areas of society.

It is clear that no one avoids learning the language, given the demands of today, because there is no doubt that learning English has become an important goal for the citizens of our country. For example, it was believed that a citizen who knows the language could find a well-paid job, travel without a language barrier and, in general, radically change his life. That is why many citizens, regardless of age, choose ways to quickly learn English and are forced to attend various language courses. This problem could be easily solved if the methodology of teaching English was widespread in the state language and it was given great importance at the pre-school, secondary and tertiary levels of the education system.

Currently, in the context of globalization and digitalization, teaching English as a foreign language in secondary educational institutions of the Kyrgyz Republic has its own characteristics. In this regard, methodological recommendations for English teachers, of course, are a guide in their teaching activities.

To increase the effectiveness of teaching English as a foreign language, you can turn to the project method (method - J. Dewey) (project method Polat E.S.). The main essence of the project method is that the student discovers new facts, understands and accepts new concepts from the teacher, and not from the

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teacher, when receiving information, so the role of the teacher here changes when using the project method: he moves from the status of an instructor to a more competent colleague, mentor.

The use of new forms of learning, when used correctly, allows us to ensure high quality education. Thus, the use of the principles of the project method in the process of teaching English as a foreign language does not have a complex impact on students, since it combines the following components: conceptual, illustrative, teaching, control parts, etc. Here, game components can facilitate the understanding and assimilation of the presented material. [1]

The goal of teaching English as a foreign language is the communicative activity of students, that is, practical knowledge of a foreign language. Project activities allow students to act as an author, creator, increase their creative potential, not only expand their general horizons, but also expand their knowledge of the language.

Thus, the popularity of the project method in teaching English as a foreign language is due to the fact that, due to its didactic nature, it allows solving the following problems:

- work on your own knowledge, use it to recognize and solve practical problems;
- walk in the information space,
- it is necessary to analyze the information received, since in the course of any cognitive, experimental or applied, creative activity, students use a complex of intellectual skills and abilities.

As in other subjects, subject and profile competencies can be formed through the use of project-based learning as a means of involving students in active cognitive, communicative, practical and other activities to solve various problems. Project-based learning fosters collaboration among students, teachers, parents, and counselors—an opportunity for real educational transformation.

There are different terms and definitions - "project-based learning", "project method", "project", "research project".

"Project teaching" is a pedagogical technology that ensures the organization of cognitive, effective and behavioral activity of students, focused on the result obtained as a result of solving a practical or theoretically important problem, including independent and group activity of students.

"Project method" - integration of knowledge and skills in various fields of science, technology and technology, solving problems using various methods and teaching aids; a way to achieve didactic goals by working through a problem in detail and obtaining a real practical result in one way or another; Pedagogical technology, arising from the needs and interests of children, their age and personal characteristics, encourages independent activity of children and independent creative activity of students.

"Project" is a technology for supporting students' independent activity in solving problems, a set of interrelated activities aimed at achieving unique results in limited time and resources. Types of projects: research, engineering-design, socio-economic, organizational.

"Research works" - create new knowledge aimed at discovering objective regularities of professional knowledge.

Thus, the term "Project" can refer not only to educational activities, but also to various areas, the term "research work" is a type of project work, and the product (result) of engineering design may not exist. [2; 3]

The outcome of project-based learning is social/ meaningful/ scientific/ technological/ entrepreneurial, etc. a specific product of value, as well as changes in the level of formation of basic competencies, established knowledge and universal learning activities.

Student interaction, joint problem solving serves to shape group norms, values and attitudes, and leadership. The project fosters communication, understanding and mutual understanding, cooperation of activities, group and inter-group cooperation, competition and positive competition. Project activity contributes to "Research culture" - problem and goal definition, action planning, information search and working with it, product creation, public speaking skills.

Project work should be structured and there are six main stages of organization:

- Determining the topic and purpose of the project, the final product (identifying the problem, what the children are interested in learning, how the results will be presented);

- Support (table, observation form, dictionary);

- Collecting information (working with sources, encyclopedias, observations, library work, Internet);

- Work with the community (specialists - librarian, doctor, social educator, parents);

- Product presentation (plan, design, presentation, promotion, etc.);

- Reflection and evaluation.

Various projects can be implemented in English lessons: research, creativity, engineering and construction, social. When implementing the project, it is necessary to take into account the language and speech skills of the students. Thus, the following projects can be offered in English lessons.

In most cases, the teacher leads the project, chooses the topic, and creates the team. This approach demotivates the students and the project becomes a teacher's task. The following conditions are necessary for project-based learning to achieve its results.

Create a theme/problem with students, i.e. ask questions so that they are interested in knowing, because the problem is different depending on the age.

Project groups are formed according to the students' choice. The topics in the same project can be different. For example, group 1 studies book genres, group 2 studies book publishing, and group 3 creates a booklet containing short stories written by students.

Students distribute roles, which allows all students to participate. For example, a designer - designs a product; 2 engineers calculate and design what and how the product will be made; accountant calculates expenses; The presenter talks about the product.

Each participant must contribute to the project. Roles in a project may change depending on the objective.

It is necessary to provide support to students in terms of content and language while performing project work. The teacher can give the students a table to fill in, write and explain the new words.

The use of project teaching in English lessons expands students' worldview, enriches vocabulary, develops critical and creative thinking, forms communication skills through practical activities, cooperation skills aimed at researching an issue of interest, and solving problems. Thus, project teaching

not only develops subject knowledge: speaking, listening, and writing skills in English. [6; 7]

Another method of teaching English as a foreign language is the motivational method. The implementation of activities and its results depend on the needs, interests and motivation of the individual. Motivation itself is aimed at goal-oriented activity through the selection and use of means and methods to achieve a specific goal. According to I.A. Zimnya, motivation is a mechanism that initiates any human activity (be it work, communication or learning). Motivation is supported and rewarded with tangible, realistic and incremental end points. Each lesson has a motivational task, and the textbooks indicate ways to improve and make the lesson more interesting, taking into account the specifics of the lesson. Among them, motivation for learning a foreign language remains one of the most important problems. Motivation researchers have shown that student motivation declines with age. The interest of students before starting to study a foreign language is very strong, and it is clear that they are eager to speak a foreign language, express their opinions and sing songs in a foreign language. They want to talk, sing, read with their friends in the language they are learning, and learn about the people of that language. Most students feel like they have entered a wonderful world when learning a foreign language. Basically, all students have a desire to speak a foreign language and learn that language, that is, motivation. Thus, when the learning process begins, most of them lose their desire. This is because the process requires a lot of hard work, and students face many challenges based on it. If there is no achievement, then motivation fades and slows down. How should we keep students interested in the lesson? This issue is balanced by considering the 3 components of teaching, i.e. We can decide by balancing 1. the activity of the student, 2. the teaching aids, 3. the activity of the teacher. Students begin to feel satisfaction by achieving some kind of achievement in their work. Motivation is the subjective world of the student, which is confirmed by the ability to understand his own demand. There is an opportunity to increase the motivation of students in foreign language teaching. It takes place on the basis of the student's interest in the language, and the student must be able to arouse his interest, understand the complexity of the language learning process, and make demands accordingly. And being a teacher just motivates to arouse the interest of that student. Scientists say that a person studies a foreign language under the influence of internal and external motivation.

Let's focus on the examples of P.M Yakobson's type of social motivation. For example: - I want to be a translator because I am good at it. I can earn a lot from this job. - With my knowledge of foreign languages, I will become a translator, because this is a very well-paid job, thanks to this job I can help my parents and support my family and live enough. Let's look at the examples of this type of motivation, but used in a negative sense: - I don't like a foreign language, but my parents say that it is necessary. Because now they are very sorry that they did not learn a foreign language well in time. They want me not to repeat the mistake they made. - I don't like a foreign language, but I have to learn it, because I have to be the leader among my peers.

Playing during the lesson also motivates to communicate in a foreign language and leads to final achievement. In today's teaching, the teacher is required to be able to arouse the motivation of the students to be active by explaining to the students how important the language they are learning is. It should bring the task to be performed closer to real life. Before giving the task to

the students, the teacher should explain specifically how to do it. If it is not clear how to perform the given task, it also reduces the interest of the students. Because if you don't fully understand how to perform the task, there is no guarantee that you will perform it. First of all, it is necessary to clearly and clearly explain how the task is to be performed: Whether it is written, spoken, or read, the teacher should say the most important thing and explain it in a language accessible to the students, not in scientific language. [4; 5]

Thus, the activity of the project method and the method of motivation in learning English as a foreign language has a number of advantages. It does not provide students with ready and unified solutions, encourages them to think independently and creatively, improves self-discipline and self-control skills. It increases students' information culture, initiative and self-esteem. From the students' point of view, this is an opportunity to maximize creative potential.

This is a method that allows us to express our thoughts individually or in a group, to test our strength, to use our knowledge, to make a profit, to show the achieved result in public.

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